

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

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With Regards

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ABSTRACT

In this digital era, face recognition system plays a vital role in almost every sector. Face recognition is one of the mostly used biometrics. It can be used for security, authentication, identification, and has got many more advantages. Despite of having low accuracy when compared to iris recognition and fingerprint recognition, it is being widely used due to its contactless and non-invasive process. Furthermore, face recognition system can also be used for attendance marking in schools, colleges, offices, etc. This system aims to build a class attendance system which uses the concept of face recognition as existing manual attendance system is time consuming and cumbersome to maintain. And there may be chances of proxy attendance. Thus, the need for this system increases. This system consists of four phases- dataset creation, face detection, face recognition, attendance updating. Dataset is created by the images of the students in class. The system is designed in TKINTER platform for GUI supported with a script of PYTHON as well as SQL database. Face detection and recognition is performed using Haar-Cascade classifier and Local Binary Pattern Histogram algorithm respectively. Faces are detected and recognized from live streaming video of the classroom. The system has output in the form of excel sheet.

Keywords- TKINTER; PYTHON; SQL; Face Recognition; Face Detection; Haar-Cascade classifier; Local Binary Pattern Histogram; attendance system;

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ABBREVIATIONS

GUI	Graphical User Interface
SQL	Structured Query Language
RFID	Radio Frequency Identifications
ERD	Entity Relationship Diagram
DFD	Data Flow Diagram
LBPH	Local Binary Pattern Histogram
CSV	Comma Separated Value
MYSQL	My Structured Query Language
OpenCV	Open-Source Computer Vision Library
HOG	Histogram of Oriented Gradients
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
SVM	Support Vector Machine
LBPH	Local Binary Patterns Histograms
SIFT	Scale Invariant Feature Transform
SURF	Speed Up Robust Feature
IDE	Integrated Development Environment
API	Applications Programming Interface
VB	Visual Basic
RAD	Rapid Application Development
NumPy	Numerical Python
QA	Quality Assurance
CCTV	Closed-Circuit Television

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The Attendance System using Face – Recognition is a replacement way method for the traditional way of marking attendance. The system is python, tkinter based system supported with MySQL database. This system can be implemented on a single faculty system of a particular institute. This system is to be based on biometrics.i.e., Face institute use the old paper or file-based system and some have adopted strategies of automated attendance system using some biometric technique. A facial recognition system is a computerized software which is suited for determining or validating a person by performing comparisons on patterns based on their facial appearances. In this system OpenCV, haar cascade and LBPH algorithm libraries were used which are one of the popular libraries for face detection by using these libraries system first capturing the student photos and storing them into the databset which were further used for the training purpose after that at the time of attendance when system camera get on system will detect the faces that were present in the frame the faces were detected by using haar cascade algorithm which were carried out in the system. after that if image that were present in the frame is tilted then LBPH algorithm will be carried out and face will be transformed to be as close as possible to perfectly centered. After that system will encode all the images that were present in the dataset as well as the face which were detected in the frame. So, at last by using OpenCV classifier will find the person in database of known peoples (i.e., capture at the starting of the project) who has closest measurements to the image that were detected by camera. After finding perfect match system will generate the name and date & time & present mark and store the entry in CSV file. Which can be further uploaded on the database and also user can open it with Microsoft Excel.

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Based on the observation, there is no available student attendance system in CITE (College of Information Technology and Engineering). CITE is still practicing the manual way of taking daily attendance. Lecturer distributes attendance sheet to be sign by student during class session or personally marked the attendance sheet one by one by

calling out student name accordingly. However, the attendance sheet can be lost easily and the whole attendance process is tending to human mistake.

Consequently, data loss may happen and the data in attendance list might be inaccurate due to deception. Besides, lecturer needs to manually analyze number of absences and calculate the percentage of present from the attendance list collected or recorded. Lecturer needs to identify number of absentees based on each subject with the respective classes that he or she taught. At the end of the semester, lecturer required to calculate the percentage of present of each student to make sure the student can take their final exam for the respective subject. Therefore, it is time-consuming and the result of calculation might go wrong when lecturer missed out some of the data in the attendance record. In addition, lecturer needs to manually write all the details about the attendance data to the appropriate documents when needed. On the other hand, attendance report also needs to be filled in by all the lecturers at the end of the semester based on each subject taught. This is to determine whether all the students met the university attendance policy before student is allow to take the final exam. However, all the attendance data need to be analyzed manually first before warning letter and attendance report document can be filled in. All this work has indirectly increased lecturers' work.

This system will automatically mark the attendance those presented in the classroom. It will reduce the manual work and avoid redundancy of data. As the attendances are maintained in registers it has been a tough task for admin and staff to maintain for long time. Instead, the software can keep long and retrieve the information when needed.

1.3 OBJECTIVES

- To implement Student attendance system based on the face recognition of webcam's image in the classroom.
- To make the attendance marking and management system efficient, time saving, simple and easy.

1.4 SCOPE AND LIMITATION

The project has got some of the following scopes:

- Finding missing people and identify predators
- Protecting businesses against theft
- Better security measures in banks and airports

- Drastically reduces human touch points
- Better tools for organizing photos

LIMITATION:

The project has got some of the following limitation:

- This Software is limited to cover only all the manual procedure involved during the attendance management.
- The accuracy of recognizing face is low due to lack of training data. However, it will increase over time.
- This system is only for single classroom. But after modification we can make it for all faculty.
- After taking attendance, the duplication of register data need to be dropped from the attendance sheet by clicking the button named 'dropped duplicate'

1.5 DEVELOPMENT METHODOLOGY

1.5.1 Agile Methodology:

Agile development model is also a type of Incremental model. Software is developed in incremental, rapid cycles. This results in small incremental releases with each release building on previous functionality. Each release is thoroughly tested to ensure software quality is maintained. It is used for time critical applications.

1.5.2 Agile Methodologies Overview:

Agile's four main values are:

- Individuals and interactions over processes and tools
- Working software over comprehensive documentation
- Customer collaboration over contract negotiation
- Responding to change over following a plan

Figure 1: Agile Model

1.6 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

With the growth in information technology, this study offers numerous values to the attendance management process in Nepal. All the records will be stored on the computer with the help of the database program.

1.7 REPORT ORGANIZATION

This project report has been organized into various chapters:

The First Chapter discusses the overall project introduction. This chapter includes the project's introduction, problem statement, objectives, scope and limitation and Development methodology has been included.

The Second Chapter of this project report has discussed the Background Study and Literature Reviews.

The Third Chapter is the main focused chapter among all the chapter where it shows the System analysis and design where it includes the functional and non-functional requirements, feasibility analysis, and lastly the main important part the algorithm used in the project.

The Fourth Chapter explains about the implementation aspect of the project, and testing the system using the different screen shots of various modules.

The Final Chapter discusses the conclusion of the project, the lesson learnt and the future recommendation.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW AND PROPOSED SYSTEM

2.1 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1.1 A Counterpart Approach to Attendance and Feedback System using Machine Learning Techniques:

In this paper, the idea of two technologies namely Student Attendance and Feedback system has been implemented with a machine learning approach. This system automatically detects the student performance and maintains the student's records like attendance and their feedback on the subjects like Science, English, etc. Therefore, the attendance of the student can be made available by recognizing the face. On recognizing, the attendance details and details about the marks of the student is obtained as feedback. [1]

2.1.2 Automated Attendance System Using Face Recognition:

Automated Attendance System using Face Recognition proposes that the system is based on face detection and recognition algorithms, which is used to automatically detects the student face when he/she enters the class and the system is capable to marks the attendance by recognizing him. Viola-Jones Algorithm has been used for face detection which detect human face using cascade classifier and PCA algorithm for feature selection and SVM for classification. When it is compared to traditional attendance marking this system saves the time and also helps to monitor the students. [2]

2.1.3 Student Attendance System Using Iris Detection:

In this proposed system the student is requested to stand in front of the camera to detect and recognize the iris, for the system to mark attendance for the student. Some algorithms like Gray Scale Conversion, Six Segment Rectangular Filter, Skin Pixel Detection is being used to detect the iris. It helps in preventing the proxy issues and it maintains the attendance of the student in an effective manner, but in one of the time-consuming processes for a student or a staff to wait until the completion of the previous members.[3]

2.1.4 Face Recognition-based Lecture Attendance System:

This paper proposes that the system takes the attendance automatically recognition obtained by continuous observation. Continuous observation helps in estimating and

improving the performance of the attendance. To obtain the attendance, positions and face images of the students present in the class room are captured. Through continuous observation and recording the system estimates seating position and location of each student for attendance marking. The work is focused on the method to obtain the different weights of each focused seat according to its location. The effectiveness of the picture is also being discussed to enable the faster recognition of the image. [4]

2.2 EXISTING RECOGNITION SYSTEM

2.2.1 Fingerprint Based recognition system:

In the Fingerprint based existing attendance system, a portable fingerprint device needs to be configured with the students fingerprint earlier. Later either during the lecture hours or before, the student needs to record the fingerprint on the configured device to ensure their attendance for the day. The problem with this approach is that during the lecture time it may distract the attention of the students. [5]

2.2.2 RFID (Radio Frequency Identification) Based recognition system:

In the RFID based existing system, the student needs to carry a Radio Frequency Identity Card with them and place the ID on the card reader to record their presence for the day. The system is capable of to connect to RS232 and record the attendance to the saved database. There are possibilities for the fraudulent access may occur. Some are students may make use of other students ID to ensure their presence when the particular student is absent or they even try to misuse it sometimes. [6]

2.2.3 Iris Based Recognition System:

In the Iris based student attendance system, the student needs to stand in front of a camera, so that the camera will scan the Iris of the student. The scanned iris is matched with data of student stored in the database and the attendance on their presence needs be updated. This reduces the paper and pen workload of the faculty member of the institute. This also reduces the chances of proxies in the class, and helps in maintaining the student records safe. It is a wireless biometric technique that solves the problem of spurious attendance and the trouble of laying the corresponding network. [3][8]

2.2.4 Face Based Recognition System:

The facial recognition technology can be used in recording the attendance through a high-resolution digital camera that detects and recognizes the faces of the students and the

machine compares the recognized face with students' face images stored in the database. Once the face of the student is matched with the stored image, then the attendance is marked in attendance database for further calculation. If the captured image doesn't match with the students' face present in the database, then this image is stored as a new image onto the database. In this system, there are possibilities for the camera to not to capture the image properly or it may miss some of the students from capturing. [2][7]

2.3 PROPOSED SYSTEM

The task of the proposed system is to capture the face of each student and to store it in the attendance dataset for their attendance. The face of the student needs to be captured in such a manner that all the feature of the students' face needs to be detected, even the seating and the posture of the student need to be recognized. There is no need for the teacher to manually take attendance in the class because the system records a video and through further processing steps the face is being recognized and the attendance sheet is updated. The algorithm processes the image captured and identifies the number of faces in the image by analyzing from the learned pattern and compare them to filter out the rest. This image processing uses multiple algorithm that takes facial features and compare them with known database.

The motivation behind this project is to simplify the means by which attendance is taken during lectures and how much time it takes. The use of ID cards or manually calling out attendance and writing it down on sheets is not productive and efficient. This system will detect the number of faces on the class and will also identify them from the store database. With the face detection and recognition system in place, it will be easy to tell if a student is actually present in the classroom or not.

CHAPTER 3

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND DESIGN

3.1 SYSTEM ANALYSIS

It is a process of observing systems for troubleshooting or developing purposes. It is an approach to information technology, where computer-based systems require defined analysis according to their makeup and design.

3.1.1 Requirement and Analysis

There are many requirements of the system which should be analyzed so that effective output can be produced with available resources.

I. Functional Requirement

The functional requirement indicates what a software system must do and how it must function. In our project, we have made an attendance system where face recognition takes place by given dataset. Some function requirements of this system are:

- Only authorized user must login to the system.
- The system must be attached to webcam and face recognition should be smooth.
- The information must be entered and managed properly.
- The administrator or the user who will use this system must login before using it.

The functional requirement can be more understood by the following user case diagram

Figure 2: Use Case Diagram

II. Non-Functional Requirement

Non-Functional will describe how a system should behave and what limits there are on its functionally. The Non-Functional requirements cover all the remaining requirements which are not covered by the functional requirements. The Non-Functional requirements of the system are given below:

CATEGORY	Non-Functional Requirement
Usability	The user will find it very easy for the programmer but difficult for the user who is not computer literate.
Reliability	The system should perform its process in an accurate way and precision to avoid problems and no data losses.
Performance	The system runs smooth and fast relying on the hardware bases of computers.
Implementation	It can be implemented on the specific computer which supports it.
Speed and Responsiveness	The system speed and responsiveness all depends upon the hardware of the computer.

3.1.2 Feasibility Analysis.

Feasibility study includes consideration of all the possible ways to provide a solution to a problem. That proposed solution should satisfy all the user requirements and should be flexible enough so that future changes can be easily done based on the future upcoming requirements.

- **Economic Feasibility**

This is a very important aspect to be considered while developing a project. We decided the technology based on the minimum possible cost factors.

- To use this web application, it doesn't require any cost.

- Overall, we have estimates that benefits the organization is going to receive from the proposed system will surely overcome the initial cost and the later on running cost for the system.

- **Technical Feasibility**

This includes the study of function, performance and constraints that may affect the ability to achieve an acceptable system. For this feasibility study, we studied complete functionality to be provided in the system and checked if everything was possible using different types of front-end and backend platform.

- **Operational Feasibility**

This project is fully GUI (Graphical User Interface) based and is very user friendly and all input to be taken are all self-explanatory even to a layman. Besides, proper training has been conducted to let the user know the essence of the system. As far as our study is concerned the clients are comfortable and happy as the system has cut down their loads and doings.

- **Gantt chart**

A Gantt chart is a project management tool that illustrates a project plan. It typically includes two sections: the left side outlines a list of tasks, while the right side has a timeline with schedule bars that visualize work. The Gantt chart can also include the start and end dates of tasks, milestones, dependencies between tasks, and assignees.

Figure 3: Gantt Chart

3.2 SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE DESIGN

Our system follows the three-tier architecture. First tier consists of GUI, Recognition tier and the Database.

3.2.1 GUI:

The GUI (Graphical User Interface) in our project deals with the interface for the teacher where he/she open the login module and can enter the main module of the system in where the system provides UI of 8 different module. Modules are Student Panel, Data Train, Face Detector, Images, Attendance, Developers, Help Support, and Exit panel.

Teacher Login: Teacher login is necessary so that unauthorized access to the application can be stopped.

Here in GUI, there is Teacher Username and Teacher Password asked for further use of application, where Teacher username and Teacher Password needs to be correct, and if that is not, application will not run. A notification Screen is also displayed giving out notification if the login is unauthorized or if the Teacher Username and Teacher Password is wrong. A login button is required for the application to process the given Teacher Username and Teacher Password for further needs. The Teacher login is necessary so that if an access is given to someone, without the correct username and password, one cannot simply run the application for his use and change the attendance of oneself without the consent of faculty or Teacher. A faculty is solely responsible for the attendance management in traditional way and here also they are.

Attendance Management System Using Facial Recognition: The main GUI where Face recognition and Face detection works is in the faculty click where Faculty can manage student details, train dataset, face recognition and manage attendance sheet of the student.

3.2.2 Trainer:

At initial level the system is trained by providing 100 images of an individual. The images are given in grey scale form and further its histogram is made to enhance the recognition accuracy. If less images are provided the accuracy will decrease and application will face difficulty to detect the face.

Detection:

Whenever any image is uploaded all the face in it are cropped and stored for further comparison. Face detection uses classifiers, which are algorithms that detects what is

either a face(1) or not a face(0) in an image. Classifiers have been trained to detect faces using thousands to millions of images in order to get more accuracy. OpenCV uses two types of classifiers, LBP (Local Binary Pattern) and Haar Cascades.

Face Recognition:

Here the detected cropped faces are compared with the trained images from the database using correlation. if any of the cropped image is recognized then that Id would be marked present in the attendance data sheet.

3.2.3 Database

We have a centralized database with all the details of student and teacher. The database is constructed using MS Excel and MySQL. Every cropped or detected image compares itself with the trained images in this database, i.e. retrieval is done and also the attendance sheet is generated on this database.

3.3 SYSTEM DESIGN

System design is the process of defining the elements of a system such as the architecture, modules and components, the different interfaces of those components and the data that goes through that system. It is meant to satisfy specific needs and requirements of a business or organization through the engineering of a coherent and well-running system.

3.3.1 E-R DIAGRAM

An Entity Relationship (ER) Diagram is a type of flowchart that illustrates how “entities” such as people, objects or concepts relate to each other within a system. ER Diagrams are most often used to design or debug relational databases in the fields of software engineering, business information systems, education and research. Also known as ERDs or ER Models, they use a defined set of symbols such as rectangles, diamonds, ovals and connecting lines to depict the interconnectedness of entities, relationships and their attributes. They mirror grammatical structure, with entities as nouns and relationships as verbs.

Figure 4: ER-Diagram

3.3.2 Data Flow Diagram (DFD)

The Data Flow Diagram shows the flow of data or information. It can be partitioned into single processes or functions. Data Flow Diagrams can be grouped together or decomposed into multiple processes. There can be physical DFD's that represent the physical files and transactions, or they can be business DFD's (logical, or conceptual).

Figure 5: Level-0 DFD

Figure 6: Level-1 DFD

3.4 ALGORITHM DETAILS

3.4.1 Introduction to Local Binary Pattern:

Local Binary Pattern (LBP) is a simple yet very efficient texture operator which labels the pixels of an image by thresholding the neighborhood of each pixel and considers the result as a binary number. Due to its discriminative power and computational simplicity, LBP texture operator has become a popular approach in various applications. It can be seen as a unifying approach to the traditionally divergent statistical and structural models of texture analysis. Perhaps the most important property of the LBP operator in real-world applications is its robustness to monotonic gray-scale changes caused, for example, by illumination variations. Another important property is its computational simplicity, which makes it possible to analyze images in challenging real-time settings.[12][13][15]

Different types of LBP algorithms:

- Eigenfaces (1991)
- Local Binary Patterns Histograms (LBPH) (1996)
- Fisherfaces (1997)
- Scale Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT) (1999)
- Speed Up Robust Features (SURF) (2006)

How LBP works:

Now that we know a little more about face recognition and the LBP, let's go further and see the steps of the algorithm:

A. Parameters:

The LBP uses 4 parameters:

- **Radius:** the radius is used to build the circular local binary pattern and represents the radius around the central pixel. It is usually set to 1.
- **Neighbors:** the number of sample points to build the circular local binary pattern. Keep in mind: the more sample points you include, the higher the computational cost. It is usually set to 8.
- **Grid X:** the number of cells in the horizontal direction. The more cells, the finer the grid, the higher the dimensionality of the resulting feature vector. It is usually set to 8.

- **Grid Y:** the number of cells in the vertical direction. The more cells, the finer the grid, the higher the dimensionality of the resulting feature vector. It is usually set to 8.

B. Training the algorithm:

First, we need to train the algorithm. To do so, we need to use a dataset with the facial images of the people we want to recognize. We need to also set an ID (it may be a number or the name of the person) for each image, so the algorithm will use this information to recognize an input image and give you an output. Images of the same person must have the same ID. With the training set already constructed, let's see the LBPH computational steps.

C. Applying the LBP Operation:

- The first computational step of the LBPH is to create an intermediate image that describes the original image in a better way, by highlighting the facial characteristics. To do so, the algorithm uses a concept of a sliding window, based on the parameter's **radius** and **neighbors**.

The image below shows this procedure:

Figure 7: Facial Image in gray scale applying LBP operation

Based on the image above, let's break it into several small steps so we can understand it easily:

- Suppose we have a facial image in grayscale.
- We can get part of this image as a window of 3x3 pixels.
- It can also be represented as a 3x3 matrix containing the intensity of each pixel (0~255).
- Then, we need to take the central value of the matrix to be used as the threshold.

- This value will be used to define the new values from the 8 neighbors.
- or each neighbor of the central value (threshold), we set a new binary value. We set 1 for values equal or higher than the threshold and 0 for values lower than the threshold.
- Now, the matrix will contain only binary values (ignoring the central value). We need to concatenate each binary value from each position from the matrix line by line into a new binary value (e.g. 10001101). Note: some authors use other approaches to concatenate the binary values (e.g. clockwise direction), but the final result will be the same.
- Then, we convert this binary value to a decimal value and set it to the central value of the matrix, which is actually a pixel from the original image.
- At the end of this procedure (LBP procedure), we have a new image which represents better the characteristics of the original image.
- **Note:** The LBP procedure was expanded to use a different number of radius and neighbors, it is called Circular LBP.

Figure 8: Circular LBP

It can be done by using **bilinear interpolation**. If some data point is between the pixels, it uses the values from the 4 nearest pixels (2x2) to estimate the value of the new data point.[11]

D. Extracting the Histograms:

Now, using the image generated in the last step, we can use the **Grid X** and **Grid Y** parameters to divide the image into multiple grids, as can be seen in the following image:

Figure 9: Extracting the histogram of each region

Based on the image above, we can extract the histogram of each region as follows:

- As we have an image in grayscale, each histogram (from each grid) will contain only 256 positions (0~255) representing the occurrences of each pixel intensity.
- Then, we need to concatenate each histogram to create a new and bigger histogram. Supposing we have 8x8 grids, we will have $8 \times 8 \times 256 = 16.384$ positions in the final histogram. The final histogram represents the characteristics of the image original image.

The LBP algorithm is pretty much it.[12]

E. Performing the face recognition:

In this step, the algorithm is already trained. Each histogram created is used to represent each image from the training dataset. So, given an input image, we perform the steps again for this new image and creates a histogram which represents the image.

- So to find the image that matches the input image we just need to compare two histograms and return the image with the closest histogram.
- We can use various approaches to compare the histograms (calculate the distance between two histograms), for example: **euclidean distance**, **chi-square**, **absolute value**, etc. In this example, we can use the Euclidean distance (which is quite known) based on the following formula:

$$D = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (hist1_i - hist2_i)^2}$$

- So the algorithm output is the ID from the image with the closest histogram. The algorithm should also return the calculated distance, which can be used as a 'confidence' measurement.

- **Note:** don't be fooled about the 'confidence' name, as lower confidences are better because it means the distance between the two histograms is closer.
- We can then use a threshold and the 'confidence' to automatically estimate if the algorithm has correctly recognized the image. We can assume that the algorithm has successfully recognized if the confidence is lower than the threshold defined.[13]

3.4.2 Introduction to Haar Cascade:

The **Viola-Jones algorithm** (also known as **Haar cascades**) is the most common algorithm in the computer vision field used for face detection on the image. The Viola-Jones algo is used not only to detect faces on images but also, we can train the model to detect different objects like cars, buildings, kitchen utensils, fruits, etc. [14]

A. Understanding Face Detector Method:

The image to be used is divided into different kinds of **sub-windows** and multiple **Haar-like features** to compute it at different scales and positions for each sub-window. The main features are selected using the **Adaboost algorithm**. Then each sub-window is checked for the **presence or absence of face** using a **cascade of classifiers**.

Example Haar features:

Figure 10: A Sample of Haar features

The detection algorithm uses a cascade of classifiers which use Haar-like features. Thus, it is also called the **Haar Cascades based detector**.

features = sum(pixels in the black area) - sum(pixels in the white area)

Figure 11: Showing how Haar Cascade works

In the figure shown above, when we calculate the second image features, it will give more features because the **bridge is lighter than the nearby area**. But if the same features, we keep on the head of the face, we will get fewer features. In the third image, we also get more features as it can detect the eye region since the eye region is darker as compared to the region below it.

It should be noted that only a single feature is not capable of detecting faces with high accuracy. But, when many such features vote for the presence or absence of a face, the detection becomes very accurate and robust.

These features have actual real importance in the context of face detection:

1. Eye regions tend to be darker than cheek regions.
2. The nose region has more bright pixels than the eye region.

Therefore, from the above given five rectangles along with the corresponding difference of sums, we are able to get the features which can classify the face. To detect which

features belong to face from the available number of features we use the AdaBoost algorithm to select which ones correspond to facial regions of an image.

As we can imagine, using the above **rectangle fixed sliding window** on the image across every **(x, y) coordinate of an image**, followed by computing all those features using Haar to classify the face features. This whole process can be computationally expensive.

To overcome this, Viola and Jones introduced cascades concept. At each stop along the sliding window path, the **window must pass a series of tests** where each subsequent test is more computationally expensive than the previous one. If any of the test fails, the window is automatically discarded.

The Haar cascade approach is good as they are very fast like Haar features and also they choose the best features of the face using the AdaBoost algorithm.

Most probably we want a solution which can detect faces on images regardless of the image size and scale and using Haar cascade we are getting the same. And finally the Viola-Jones algorithm is able to detect objects in real-time.

B. Limitation of Haar Cascade:

We have seen haar cascade performing very well, but there are several limitations of haar cascade.

- High false-positive detection
- Less accurate than deep learning-based techniques
- Manual tuning of parameters.
- Training haar cascade on a custom object is not easy.

CHAPTER 4

IMPLEMENTATION AND TESTING

4.1 IMPLEMENTATION

4.1.1 Tools Used:

Different tools, applications and technologies have been used in this project. And all of them are discussed below:

- **Microsoft Visual Studio:**

Microsoft Visual Studio is an Integrated Development Environment (IDE) developed by Microsoft to develop GUI (Graphical user interface), console, web application, web apps, mobile apps, cloud, and web server, etc. With the help of this IDE, you can create manage a code as well as native code. It uses the various platforms of Microsoft Software development software like windows store, Microsoft Silverlight, and Windows API, etc. It is not a language-specific IDE as you can use this to write code in c#, c++, VB (Visual Basic), Python, JavaScript, and many more languages. It provides support for 36 different programming languages. For convenient to develop our project we used this tool which is very aidful for us.[19]

- **Apache:**

The Apache HTTP Server Project is an effort to develop and maintain an open-source HTTP server for modern operating systems including UNIX and Windows. The goal of this project is to provide a secure, efficient and extensible server that provides HTTP services in sync with the current HTTP standards.[18]

- **MySQL:**

MySQL server is an open-source relational database management system which is a major support for web-based applications. Databases and related tables are the main component of many websites and applications as the data is stored and exchanged over the web. Even all social networking websites mainly Facebook, Twitter, and Google depend on MySQL data which are designed and optimized for such purpose. For all these reasons, MySQL server becomes the default choice for web applications.

MySQL server is used for data operations like querying, sorting, filtering, grouping, modifying and joining the tables. Before learning the commonly used queries, let us look into some of the advantages of MySQL.[17]

Front End:

- **Tkinter:**

Tkinter is the inbuilt python module that is used to create GUI applications. It is one of the most commonly used modules for creating GUI applications in Python as it is simple and easy to work with. You don't need to worry about the installation of the Tkinter module separately as it comes with Python already. It gives an object-oriented interface to the Tk GUI toolkit.[16]

Back End:

- **Python:**

In technical terms, Python is an object-oriented, high-level programming language with integrated dynamic semantics primarily for web and app development. It is extremely attractive in the field of Rapid Application Development because it offers dynamic typing and dynamic binding options.[16]

- To check whether software is built. It is as per the requirement or not.
- Finding defects from the software before customers find them out.
- Defects get a fix from the developer.
- Preventing defects.
- Gaining confidence about the level of quality.

- **NumPy:**

NumPy is a library for the Python programming language, adding support for large, multidimensional arrays and matrices along with a large collection of high-level mathematical functions to operate on these arrays. NumPy stands for Numerical Python. NumPy is a Python library used for working with arrays. It also has functions for working in the domain of linear algebra, Fourier transform, and matrices. The core functionality of NumPy is its "ND array", for n-dimensional array, data structure. These arrays are stride views on memory. In contrast to Python's built-in list data structure, these arrays are homogeneously typed: all elements of a single array must be of the same type.[16]

- **Pandas:**

Pandas is a software library written for the Python programming language for data manipulation and analysis. In particular, it offers data structures and operations for manipulating numerical tables and time series. Data Frame object for data manipulation with integrated indexing. Tools for reading and writing data between in-memory data structures and different file formats. Pandas is mainly used for data analysis. Pandas allows importing data from various file formats such as comma-separated value, JSON, SQL database tables or queries, and Microsoft Excel. Pandas allow various data manipulation operations such as merging, reshaping, selecting, as well as data cleaning, and data wrangling features.[16]

- **OpenCV:**

OpenCV is a huge open-source library for computer vision, machine learning, and image processing. OpenCV supports a wide variety of programming languages like Python, C++, Java, etc. It can process images and videos to identify objects, faces, or even the handwriting of a human. When it is integrated with various libraries, such as Numpy which is a highly optimized library for numerical operations, then the number of weapons increases in your Arsenal i.e., whatever operations one can do in Numpy can be combined with OpenCV.

This OpenCV tutorial will help you learn the Image-processing from Basics to Advance, like operations on Images, Videos using a huge set of Opencv-programs and projects.[16]

4.1.2 Implementation details of modules:

- **Registration Module.**

This Modules help to register the new user to the desktop application and also help to store the user enter data into the MySQL. In which it helps to give access to the user into the desktop application. It also checks whether the user is already there or not into the database so there will be no two named persons in the single desktop application.

Operation provided by this model system are:

- register():

In this function, new teacher can register his/her details in where a form display. He/she needs to provide first name, last name,

contact, email (user name), for password reset security question, and password. And the data are stored into database.

- **Login / Logout Module.**

This Modules helps to login in or logout from the desktop application where you have to enter the record you have entered in the registration form. If the enter record is matched to the database, then it will lead the user to the home page of application if not correct then it will be in the login page until and unless the enter data is matched with the database record it will not redirect to the homepage of the application. If he/she forgets password then by calling function, can be reset password easily using security question.

Operational provided by this model system are:

- login()
- reset_password()
- fotget_password()

- **Main Module.**

This module is the main interface of the system in where teacher can perform different operation. It includes 8 different buttons from where different task can be achieved. The functions defined in this model are listed below:

- student_panel()
- train_panel()
- face_recognition()
- attendance_panel()
- developer()
- helpSupport()
- open_img()
- iExit()

- **Student Module.**

Teacher can add, update, delete and take photo of students in this model. The details of students which include department, course they choose, year duration,

semester, student id, name, division, roll, gender, date of birth, email, mobile number, address and tutor name. The student id, roll number and email must be different from other.

Operation provided by this model system are:

- add_data()
- fetch_data()
- get_cursor()
- update_data()
- delete_data()
- reset_data()
- generate_dataset()

- **Train Module.**

This module is use to train the captured images using LBP classifier. The main work of the system is done by this module. It will store the dataset of the images pixel into a csv file called clf.xml. From the selected id of the student, it will do the operation. The function we used in this module:

- train_classifier()

- **Face Recognition Module.**

Another main module of the system which main aim is to detect and recognition faces. In this module, using the algorithm named Haar Cascade it will detect the face, and from classifier it will fetch the data using LBP algorithm to recognize the face. If the histogram match between them then it will show the student id, roll and name on the screen then marked attendance in the attendance sheet. Otherwise for unknow face, it will show the face as unknown in screen.

The operations made on this module are:

- mark_attendance()
- face_recognize()
- recognize()

- **Attendance Module.**

Teacher can import the attendance sheet to view, update or to store into database. And also update and delete the attendance to/from database easily. And he/she can export the sheet.

The operations used:

- update_data()
- delete_data()
- fetch_data()
- reset_data()
- importCsv()
- exportCsv()
- get_cursor_left()
- get_cursor_right()
- action()

- **Developer Module.**

Contain the details of the developer team.

- **Help Support Module.**

Link of the support team.

4.2 TESTING

4.2.1 Purpose of Testing:

The purpose of testing is to help in finalizing the software application or product against business and user requirements. It is very important to have good test coverage in order to test the software application completely and make it sure that it's performing well as per the specifications. Testing can be verification and validation or reliability estimation. Some of the objectives of software testing are given below:

- To check whether software is built. It is as per the requirement or not.
- Finding defects from the software before customers find them out.
- Defects get a fix from the developer.
- Preventing defects.
- Gaining confidence about the level of quality.

4.2.2 Test case for Unit Testing:

Table 1: Register Page

Objectives	To register the record of the user for the login purpose.
Action	The input section should be filled with the Full Name, Contact, Email, Security Question, and the Password should be hidden.
Excepted Results	To enter all the data correctly which stores the data into the database and pressing the Register button should redirect to the login page.
Actual Results	All user data is inserted into the input field and all data is stored into the database and the button redirects to the login page.
Conclusion	Test Successful.

Registration

First Name: <input type="text" value="Rukesh"/>	Contact No: <input type="text" value="9861116929"/>
Last Name: <input type="text" value="Duwal"/>	Email: <input type="text" value="iamrukeshduwal@gmail.com"/>
Select Security Question: <input type="text" value="Your Date of Birth"/>	Password: <input type="password" value="*****"/>
Security Answer: <input type="password" value="****"/>	Confirm Password: <input type="password" value="*****"/>
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> I Agree the Terms & Conditions	
<input type="button" value="Register"/>	<input type="button" value="Login"/>

Success ×

Successfully Registered!

Figure 12: Registration Panel

Login

Username:

Password:

Login

[Register](#) [Forget](#)

Figure 13: Login Panel

Table 2: Login Page

Objectives	To login the system for entering the main page of the project.
Action	Enter the user email and password, pressing the login button leads to the main page.
Excepted Results	To enter the Email and Password of the user and if the email and password matched in the database then login to the main page.
Actual Results	The email and password are verified and entered into the main page.
Conclusion	Test Successful.

Figure 14: Login Successful

Figure 15: Attendance Management System Using Facial Recognition Panel

Table 3: Student Panel

Objectives	To manage the record of student details
Action	Adding, Updating, Deleting, and Taking Photo of Student
Excepted Results	Provide the student details along with images for face detection and recognition.
Actual Results	All the student details stored into database and images into folder.
Conclusion	Test Successful.

Figure 16: Student Panel

Figure 17: Student Details Successful

Figure 18: Student Details Update

Figure 19: Student Details Updated

Figure 20: Student Details Delete panel

Figure 21: Student Detail Deleted

Figure 22: Image Dataset

Table 4: Train Dataset

Objectives	To train the images that had been taken from students
Action	Train Dataset and save images pixel into classifier file
Excepted Results	Data should be trained and saved image pixel into classifier file.
Actual Results	Saved image pixel into classifier file
Conclusion	Test Successful.

Figure 23: Training Panel

```

cf.xml
1  <?xml version="1.0"?>
2  <opencv_storage>
3  <opencv_lbphfaces>
4    <threshold>1.7976931348623157e+308</threshold>
5    <radius>1</radius>
6    <neighbors>8</neighbors>
7    <grid_x>8</grid_x>
8    <grid_y>8</grid_y>
9    <histograms>
10     <_ type_id="opencv-matrix">
11       <rows>1</rows>
12       <cols>16384</cols>
13       <dt>f</dt>
14       <data>
15         1.7361111e-02 1.7361111e-03 1.7361111e-03 1.7361111e-03
16         1.2152778e-02 0. 0. 1.7361111e-03 0. 0. 0. 3.4722225e-03
17         1.7361111e-03 1.0416667e-02 8.6805559e-03 8.6805559e-03 0.
18         0. 1.7361111e-03 0. 0. 1.0416667e-02 0. 1.7361111e-03
19         0. 8.5069447e-02 1.7361111e-03 3.2986111e-02 2.7777780e-02
20         1.7361111e-03 0. 0. 0. 1.7361111e-03 0. 0. 0. 0. 0. 0.
21         0. 1.7361111e-03 5.2083334e-03 1.7361111e-03 0. 0. 0. 0.
22         0. 1.7361111e-03 4.1666667e-02 0. 0. 0. 1.2673611e-01 0.
23         5.2083332e-02 1.2152778e-02 5.2083334e-03 0. 0. 0. 0. 0.
24         0. 1.7361111e-03 0. 0. 0. 0. 1.7361111e-03 1.7361111e-03
25         0. 0. 0. 0. 0. 0. 0. 0. 0. 1.7361111e-03
26         1.7361111e-03 0. 1.7361111e-03 5.2083334e-03 0. 0. 0. 0.

```

Figure 24: Classifier

Table 5: Face Detector

Objectives	To detect face that had been trained and make attendance for known faces only
Action	Face recognizes using LBPH Algorithm and take attendance into attendance sheet
Excepted Results	Faces should be recognized and take attendance
Actual Results	Recognize the faces and make attendance
Conclusion	Test Successful.

Figure 25: Face Recognition

Figure 26: Unknown Face Recognition

```
attendance.csv
1 Roll,ID,Name,Time,Date,Status
2 1,1, Rukesh, 19:28:23, 20/08/2022, Present
3
```

Figure 27: Student Datasheet

Table 6: Attendance Manage

Objectives	To manage attendance sheet
Action	Import, Export, Update and Delete Attendance sheet. Also manage attendance to database
Excepted Results	Manage Attendance sheet along with mange into database
Actual Results	Recognize the faces and make attendance
Conclusion	Test Successful.

Figure 28: Attendance CSV

Figure 29: Records Saved in Database

Table 7: Exit

Objectives	To exit the system
Action	Click on exit button
Excepted Results	Close the application
Actual Results	Closed application
Conclusion	Test Successful.

Figure 30: Exit Panel

4.2.3 Test case for System Testing:

System testing is a process of testing the entire system that is fully functional, in order to ensure the system is bound to all the requirements provided by the client in the form of the functional specification or system specification documentation. In most cases, it is done next to the Integration testing, as this testing should be covering the end-to-end system's actual routine. So, the System Testing is divided into two testing that is:

- Alpha Testing

Alpha testing is the final stage of testing performed by your QA team to check that your application is ready for release outside your company. The testing is coordinated in-house, structured and is usually done by your own test team. Alpha testing is predominantly about ensuring bug-free functionality.

This testing is done very carefully for the bug-free. While doing this we found different bugs and some of the bugs have been solved. A few bugs are still needed to be fixed. The bugs that are there like (popup bugs and posts that are not posted even though the data is positive.). There are a few bugs that we are working to solve. The bug is while there are no student details in database but tried to recognize the face then the system gets error.

But the bugs do not affect the performance of the system a little bit. so, we can say that it is ready to be released in the real world.

- Beta Testing

Beta testing involves releasing the software to a limited number of real users. They are free to use it as they want. In other words, this testing is unstructured. However, the users are encouraged to give feedback about how the application performs. Usually, you will also monitor how the backend is performing during these tests. Beta testing is more focused on performance and scalability.

So, for the beta testing we have given access to the beta project to a few friends for a week then after a week the feedback is taken from the users. The feedback was the UI and the color coordination is very well and the working process is smooth. And, also the details of student can be maintained and store in database easily. The only drawback is that the project has the bugs that while recognizing the face without the details in database. But, after solving the bugs it is a very good application for attendance system using facial recognition which is perfect for the real-world project.

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 CONCLUSION

In order to maintain the attendance this system has been developed. It replaces the manual system with an automated system which is fast, efficient, cost and time saving as replaces the stationary material and the paper work. Hence this system is expected to give desired results and in future could be implemented for logout. Also, the efficiency could be improved by integrating other techniques with it in near future.

In this system we have implemented an attendance record to assist Faculty. It saves time and effort, especially if it is a lecture with huge number of students. Automated Attendance System has been envisioned for the purpose of reducing the drawbacks in the traditional (manual) system.

This attendance system using facial recognition demonstrates the use of image processing techniques in classroom. This system can not only merely help in the attendance system, but also improve the goodwill of an institution.

5.2 LESSON LEARNT/OUTCOME

While making this project we have learnt many things. And they are listed down below:

- Learn about the openCV and python.
- Learn how to train the data using supervised learning.
- Learn to solve the errors found in the project.
- Learn to communicate with the team.
- Learn to make a workable real time project.

5.3 FUTURE RECOMMENATIONS

The system can be made more flexible and scalable using these recommendations. Please note that the system implemented here is just a prototype of idea presented via this project. The recommendations are as follows:

- The system can be extended to a greater number of students with freedom to change list of students according to class changes.
- The system can be made more flexible to allow updating of templates in case student incurs significant amount of change in his facial features.

- The system can also be extended to allow better face recognition algorithm in which even rotational features of face can be detected efficiently.
- Absentee to get Email
- Camera Access by CCTV rather Web cam.
- Get an ID card with name, class, ID, Barcode and Photo on it.
- Student can access his/her attendance dates individually to his Email account
- More Authority to the Admin like, add or remove Faculty, update student details etc.
- Semester and Class wise access to Faculty
- More than one Faculty can Access the Application

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